

Comparison between Topical Corticosteroids vs Topical tacrolimus in the management of atopic dermatitis in children.

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic, relapsing inflammatory skin condition, mostly seen among children, which manifests with symptoms such as pruritus and eczematous lesions. This study has been carried out to compare the effectiveness of topical corticosteroids and topical tacrolimus on children affected with mild to moderate atopic dermatitis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This prospective comparative study was conducted from February 2025 to January 2026 at a rural tertiary care hospital in South India. A total of 120 children aged 2–12 years with mild to moderate atopic dermatitis were included and divided into two groups: topical corticosteroid group (n=60) and topical tacrolimus group (n=60). Disease severity was assessed using the SCORAD index at baseline, 1 week, 2 weeks, and 3 weeks. Statistical analysis was performed using Independent sample t-test and Chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant..

RESULTS:

The baseline demographics of the patients as well as the clinical factors were statistically similar in both groups ($p > 0.05$). Improvement in SCORAD was observed in both groups over the course of treatment but the effect of tacrolimus was significantly

greater in 2nd and 3rd week ($p<0.05$). Reduction in pruritus was significantly greater in tacrolimus group (54 vs 46; $p<0.05$). Atrophy occurred in only corticosteroid group (8 cases). Burning sensation occurred more in tacrolimus group (12 cases; $p<0.05$).

CONCLUSION:

Topical tacrolimus is a safe and more effective alternative to corticosteroids in pediatric atopic dermatitis, offering superior clinical improvement and avoiding steroid-induced adverse effects.

KEYWORDS:

Atopic dermatitis, Tacrolimus, Corticosteroids, SCORAD, Pruritus, Children

INTRODUCTION

Atopic dermatitis (AD) or atopic eczema is a chronic inflammatory skin disease (AD) characterized by extreme itching, dry skin (xerosis), and/ or red, itchy, and inflamed skin (eczematous lesions) ¹. It is associated with immunodysregulation, epidermal barrier dysfunction, and genetic predisposition, often coexisting with other atopic conditions such as asthma and allergic rhinitis ². The disease typically begins in early childhood, with nearly 85% of cases presenting before five years of age, and significantly impacts quality of life due to sleep disturbances, recurrent flares, and psychosocial stress ³. Due to the negative effect on the patient's quality of life (e.g., sleep disruption) as well as the increased risk of psychological distress from the disease, the chronic nature of AD requires long-term treatment plans to keep the patient from developing additional disease activity and symptoms.

Atopic dermatitis is one of the most commonly diagnosed dermatological conditions in children (15-30%), and has been increasing in prevalence over the past few decades (both in pediatric and adult populations) ^{4,5}. In pediatric populations, prevalence ranges between 5% and 20% depending on geographic and environmental factors ⁶. The estimated prevalence of AD in children in India is approximately 15-23%, with potential increases in prevalence due to urbanization, environmental pollution, and changes in lifestyle ^{7,8}.

Epidermal barrier dysfunction, TH2/ eosinophilic immune dysfunction, and environmental factors all play a role in the pathophysiology of AD⁹. Skin barrier protein defects, such as filaggrin, lead to increased trans epidermal water loss and penetration of allergens through the skin, and continue to perpetuate and maintain inflammation and itching. Microbial colonization of the skin, especially by *Staphylococcus aureus*, contributes further to increased disease severity. These mechanisms highlight the need for therapies that are both anti-controlled and restorative of the barrier in order to treat the skin disorder.

Topical corticosteroids (TCS) have formed the basis of treatment for atopic dermatitis for many years, as TCS have both potent anti-inflammatory effects and can rapidly control symptoms, making them the first-line treatment option¹⁰. When used correctly, more than 80% of patients will show improvement with TCS usage for the control of disease activity. With long-term use of TCS, patients experience multiple significant side effects such as skin atrophy, striae, telangiectasia, and risk of systemic absorption (particularly in children), raising concerns regarding long-term use and adherence to therapy. This has led to the need for safe, nonsteroidal, and effective alternative forms of therapy.

Tacrolimus and other topical calcineurin inhibitors (TCIs) have emerged as an effective non steroidal agents in atopic dermatitis treatment¹¹. Tacrolimus works by inhibiting T-cell activation and the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, resulting in decreased inflammation without causing atrophy. Tacrolimus is helpful to use in sensitive areas, including the face and flexures, and as a long-term maintenance therapy. Recent studies have shown comparable efficacy between tacrolimus and topical corticosteroids in moderate-to-severe disease, with improved safety profiles in long-term use^{12,13}. Given these advantages, a comparative evaluation of topical corticosteroids and tacrolimus in pediatric atopic dermatitis is essential to optimize treatment strategies and improve patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This current prospective comparative study was undertaken from February 2025 to January 2026 in the Department of Paediatrics at a rural tertiary care hospital in South India. This study involved the selection of patients between the ages of 2 and 12

years who were suffering from atopic dermatitis and were being treated in the out-patient dermatology department during the course of this study. Diagnosis was made based on clinical diagnosis, and details regarding age, sex, socio-economic status, atopic familial history, duration of illness, site of skin lesions, and history of past treatment were noted using a structured questionnaire. In total, 120 subjects with atopic dermatitis were included in this study, and these subjects were divided according to their topical treatment as follows:

Group I: Topical corticosteroids (n=60)

Group II: Topical tacrolimus (n=60)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children in the age group of 2-12 years
- Children with a diagnosis of mild to moderate atopic dermatitis
- Symmetrical lesions in children that are suitable for assessing treatment efficacy
- Children whose parents/guardians gave informed written consent for participation in the study

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with a diagnosis of severe atopic dermatitis warranting systemic treatment
- Children with superimposed bacterial, viral or fungal infections of the skin
- Children suffering from other chronic skin diseases like psoriasis, ichthyosis and seborrheic dermatitis
- Children undergoing systemic corticosteroids, immunosuppressive therapy or phototherapy within the last four weeks prior to the study
- Children allergic to topical corticosteroids or tacrolimus
- Children whose parents/guardians did not give consent for participation

Study Procedure:

Following consent from the parents or guardians, all eligible children underwent thorough clinical examination at baseline. Severity of the disease was measured by the SCORAD (SCORing Atopic Dermatitis) index¹⁴ which is an extensively validated and

reliable clinical method of assessing skin involvement in terms of extent (A: 0-100, on the basis of rule of nines), intensity (B: 0-18, erythema, edema, oozing, excoriation, lichenification and dryness), and associated pruritus or sleeplessness (C: 0-20), giving a maximal score of 103. The total score was determined using the formula: $SCORAD = A/5 + 7B/2 + C$, while the severity of atopic dermatitis was classified as mild (<25), moderate (25-50), and severe (>50). Baseline photographs were taken after consent wherever applicable for objective comparison during follow-up.

Children in Group 1 were given hydrocortisone 1% cream or mometasone furoate 0.1% cream, depending on the lesion severity and location, applied as a thin layer over affected parts twice a day in combination with an emollient.

Children in Group 2 were given topical tacrolimus 0.03% ointment, applied twice a day over the affected parts in addition to the emollient therapy. The duration of treatment was three weeks, the same period that was used in a recently conducted pediatric trial in which tacrolimus was compared with hydrocortisone.

Children were reviewed at baseline, week 1, week 2, and week 3. For each child, SCORAD score, pruritus score, percentage of lesion improvement, burning sensation, erythema, skin irritation, and cutaneous atrophy were recorded. The primary end point was the decrease in SCORAD score at the completion of the treatment from the baseline. Other end points were reduction in pruritus score, physician's assessment of response to the treatment, improvement in the clinical condition based on parental report, short-term recurrence rate, and any adverse reactions experienced.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS version 25.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables were expressed as frequency and percentage. Intergroup comparison of continuous variables was performed using the Independent sample t-test, while categorical variables were analysed using the Chi-square test wherever appropriate. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Variable	Category	Corticosteroid (n=60)	Tacrolimus (n=60)	p-value
Age Group	2–5 years	18	20	0.72
	6–9 years	24	22	0.68
	10–12 years	18	18	1.00
Gender	Male	34	32	0.71
	Female	26	28	0.71
Family History of Atopy	Present	36	38	0.71
	Absent	24	22	0.71

Table 1: Demographic Profile and Family History of Atopy

As seen in Table 1, the age distribution, gender, and family history of atopy were comparable between the corticosteroid and tacrolimus groups, with no statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$). The Chi-square test was used for analysis of categorical variables.

Variable	Category	Corticosteroid (n=60)	Tacrolimus (n=60)	p-value
Duration of Illness	<1 year	22	20	0.68
	1–3 years	26	28	0.72
	>3 years	12	12	1.00
Site of Lesions	Flexural	30	32	0.71
	Extensor	18	16	0.67
	Generalized	12	12	1.00
Previous Treatment	Yes	40	42	0.68
	No	20	18	0.68

Table 2: Clinical Profile of Study Population

As seen in Table 2, clinical parameters including duration of illness, site of lesions, and previous treatment history were similarly distributed in both groups, showing no significant difference ($p>0.05$). The Chi-square test was applied for comparison.

Parameter	Corticosteroid (Mean \pm SD)	Tacrolimus (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
SCORAD Score (Baseline)	42.8 \pm 6.4	43.5 \pm 5.9	0.54

Table 3: Baseline SCORAD Score Comparison

As seen in Table 3, the mean baseline SCORAD scores in the corticosteroid and tacrolimus groups were comparable, indicating similar disease severity at the start of treatment ($p=0.54$). The Independent sample t-test was used for comparison.

Time Interval	Corticosteroid (Mean \pm SD)	Tacrolimus (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Baseline	42.8 \pm 6.4	43.5 \pm 5.9	0.54
1 Week	34.2 \pm 5.8	32.6 \pm 5.2	0.09
2 Weeks	26.5 \pm 4.9	23.8 \pm 4.6	<0.05
3 Weeks	19.8 \pm 4.2	16.2 \pm 3.9	<0.05

Table 4: Reduction in SCORAD Score Over Follow-up

As seen in Table 4, both groups showed a progressive reduction in SCORAD scores over time; however, the tacrolimus group demonstrated significantly greater improvement at 2 and 3 weeks ($p<0.05$). The Independent sample t-test was used to compare mean scores.

Variable	Category	Corticosteroid (n=60)	Tacrolimus (n=60)	p-value
Pruritus Improvement	Improved	46	54	<0.05

Variable	Category	Corticosteroid (n=60)	Tacrolimus (n=60)	p-value
	Not Improved	14	6	<0.05
Burning Sensation	Present	3	12	<0.05
Skin Atrophy	Present	8	0	<0.05
Erythema/Irritation	Present	5	10	0.17

Table 5: Pruritus Improvement and Adverse Effects

As seen in Table 5, pruritus improvement was significantly higher in the tacrolimus group, while skin atrophy was more frequently observed in the corticosteroid group ($p < 0.05$). The Chi-square test was used for analysis of categorical outcomes.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, demographic features including age, sex, and atopic history within families were comparable in the two groups ($p > 0.05$). The similarity of the above factors in the two groups ensured that they were well-matched and thus suitable for comparison.

Moreover, the clinical characteristics such as duration of illness, location of lesion, and prior use of treatment were also comparable ($p > 0.05$) among the two groups. In other words, disease profile and prior exposure to treatment would not interfere with their outcomes. The SCORAD scores before treatment between the groups on corticosteroids and tacrolimus were comparable (42.8 ± 6.4 vs 43.5 ± 5.9 , $p = 0.54$). This was because of the fact that the disease severity was similar in the two groups before the onset of the study. However, the SCORAD scores were progressively reduced with the use of both drugs but showed more improvement in the latter during weeks 2 and 3 ($p < 0.05$) and were in agreement with results reported by Arkwright PD et al ¹⁵, who reported the superior efficacy of tacrolimus in 77% of children with moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis.

In a similar pattern, Reitamo S et al.'s ¹⁶study revealed statistically significant superiority of both 0.03% and 0.1% tacrolimus over hydrocortisone ($p < 0.001$). The same pattern was reflected in our results, as well as a superior efficacy compared to topical corticosteroids supporting its higher efficacy.

The systematic review by Pena J et al. ¹⁷, proved the higher efficacy of tacrolimus compared to weak topical corticosteroids in the majority of published studies. Our results of significantly higher SCORAD index reduction and overall efficacy align with these findings.

In terms of symptomatic Improvement, pruritis relief was much better with tacrolimus (54 vs 46; $p < 0.05$), which is very important clinically as pruritis sensations are among the hardest symptoms in patients with atopic dermatitis.

Regarding safety issues, skin atrophy was noted exclusively in the topical corticosteroid group (8 cases) with no adverse effects was observed with tacrolimus ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, however, burning sensation was observed much more often with tacrolimus (12 vs 3 cases; $p < 0.05$). These findings are consistent with Reitamo et al. ¹⁶, who found an increased incidence of burning sensation in those treated with tacrolimus and Pena et al. ¹⁷ who emphasized on the benefit of tacrolimus in not leading to any skin atrophy due to steroids.

The study by Harvey J et al. ¹⁸ reported that although tacrolimus may offer efficacy similar to weak corticosteroids in the short term, it is also associated with potential side effects. On the other hand, our study indicated superiority of tacrolimus in terms of efficacy and validated burning sensation as one of the common side effects.

Similarly, Langa Y et al. ¹⁹ reported that even though corticosteroids are the primary choice of therapy, their prolonged usage is limited by side effects; on the contrary, tacrolimus can effectively control the disease condition without leading to any problems seen with steroids.. This is supported by our findings, where tacrolimus showed superior efficacy with absence of skin atrophy.

Overall, this study demonstrates that the use of tacrolimus topically is safe and more efficacious than the use of topical corticosteroids in managing pediatric patients

with atopic dermatitis, particularly in terms of lowering disease severity and relieving itching without adverse effects.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, both topical corticosteroids and tacrolimus were effective in managing pediatric atopic dermatitis; however, tacrolimus showed superior improvement in disease severity and pruritus. It also avoided steroid-related adverse effects such as skin atrophy, making it a safer alternative for long-term use, especially in sensitive areas.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AD: Atopic Dermatitis; TCS: Topical Corticosteroids; SCORAD: SCORing Atopic Dermatitis; SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences; OPD: Outpatient Department; SD: Standard Deviation; TH2: T helper 2; p-value: Probability - value.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

Ethical Committee approval was obtained from the Institute viz. No.P/2025/70. The study protocol for Medical Research involving human subjects was approved under the Declaration of Helsinki.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS:

All authors contributed substantially to the conception and design of the study, data collection, analysis and interpretation of data, and drafting of the manuscript. The corresponding author was primarily responsible for study supervision, manuscript preparation, and final approval of the version to be submitted. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Written informed consent for publication of anonymized clinical data and photographs, wherever applicable, was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants prior to enrolment in the study.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS:

The authors declare that they used generative AI and/or AI-assisted technologies only for language refinement, grammar correction, and improvement of readability during manuscript preparation.

Competing Interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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